

EUROPEANA Media

Document: First Iteration Usability Evaluation Report
FINAL (16 August, 2019)

ACTIVITY 3: USABILITY EVALUATION

Produced under the Grant agreement No INEA/CEF/ICT/A2017/1564684 Europeana Media for
the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency

Department C – Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) – TELECOMMUNICATIONS SECTOR

This project is co-funded by
the European Union

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
Methodology	4
Preamble	4
Participants.....	5
Tasks Presentation and Analysis	6
Introductory Questions	6
Findings and Recommendations	10
Video Embed	10
Video Subtitling	11
Video Annotation	11
Video Playlist	12
Item Page Issues	14
Performance Metrics.....	15
Task Complete Rate.....	15
Task Complete Time	17
Problem Severity	18
Task Level Satisfaction.....	20
Overall System Satisfaction	23
Recommendations.....	24
Post-test Interview	27
Conclusions.....	28
Appendix 1: Usability evaluation tasks.....	29
Usability tasks.....	29
Educator user group	29
Researcher user group	32
General public	35
Appendix 2: Pre-test questionnaire	38
Appendix 3: Data logger screenshot of educator user group tasks list.....	40
Appendix 4: Workload rating scale definitions according to NASA -TLX.....	41

Executive Summary

The first iteration usability test of the Europeana Enhanced Unified Player prototype took place from 4-6 June 2019 at the Media and Learning Conference in Leuven. Five test persons from the general public and five persons from the user group of educators participated in the test in Leuven. On 11 June 2019, there was a test with one researcher in Hannover and on 13 June 2019 with three researchers in Berlin. The first version of the prototype has four basic functionalities namely embedding, annotating, subtitling, and playlist creation. These functionalities were tested during the usability test with Educators and the General Public user groups in Leuven and later with the user group of Researchers in Hannover and Berlin. The overall goal of the test was to determine whether or not the unified media player prototype meets the usage requirements, and applicable dialogue principles, heuristics and design rules.

All the 14 participants took all the tasks presented and completed them successfully and in few cases with assistance for embedding video, video annotation, and subtitle tasks. The tasks of video embed and subtitling had to be skipped for one participant from the educator user group as a result of being presented with a different task mockup. It was decided not to disrupt the session, and the participant had to continue with the other tasks. Nevertheless, there is no significant negative impact on the group and overall results. The major issues experienced by most of the participants include confusion between the large view and full-screen buttons when previewing annotations in default and large view modes. Some buttons such as the copy-button, to copy embed code were also not well-perceived by almost all the participants. Overall, the learning curve of the unified player and editor is not steep, and users can learn to use the video player and editor quickly. Nevertheless, changes should be made to improve the design of both the video player and editor as well as information presentation on the item page.

Methodology

Preamble

The usability evaluation of the Enhanced Unified Media Player (EUPS) was conducted by Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) in Leuven, Belgium from 5-6 June 2019 and subsequently in Hannover and Berlin, Germany on 11 June and 13 June 2019 respectively. The tests in Leuven took place during the 2019 Media and Learning Conference. Three of the educator user group participants were attendees at the conference. A laptop computer with the unified media player prototype and supporting Europeana item page was used in a typical office environment. The following questions were raised for the usability evaluation:

1. To what extent is the interaction architecture and design of the unified media player comprehensible to users?
2. Can the different user groups solve typical usage tasks satisfactorily?
3. Is the use of the unified media player comprehensible for the users even without a long acclimatization phase? (intuitiveness)
4. Are all controls recognized and understood?
5. Can users find all the information they need in the unified player?

The usability evaluation objectives were:

1. Determine design inconsistencies and usability problem areas within the user interface and content areas of the unified player and item page. Potential sources of error may include:
 - a. Navigation errors – failure to locate functions, excessive keystrokes to complete a function, failure to follow recommended screen flow.
 - b. Presentation errors – failure to locate and properly act upon desired information in screens, selection errors due to labeling ambiguities.
 - c. Control usage problems – improper toolbar or entry field usage.
2. Exercise the web application under controlled test conditions with representative users. Data will be used to access whether usability goals regarding an effective, efficient, and well-received player interface have been achieved.
3. Establish baseline user performance and user-satisfaction levels of the player interface for future usability evaluations.

During the usability evaluation, fourteen participants, matching the user group profiles, spent on average one hour with the media player mockup both in playing mode on mockup Europeana item page and in editing mode. During this hour, participants:

- Completed a user background online questionnaire (<https://forms.gle/di24huBjrXWnZj497>);
- Performed real-world tasks with the player while thinking aloud (the tasks list is in Table 6 and user stories are in Appendix 1);
- Answered questions about their overall satisfaction;
- Answered questions about initial site impressions.

The participants' interactions with the prototype were monitored by the facilitator seated in the same office. A note taker/data logger also monitored the sessions as an observer in the same room. The test sessions were also videotaped.

The facilitator briefed the participants on the unified media player prototype and assured that they were evaluating the system, and the participants were not being evaluated. All the participants signed an informed consent that

acknowledges: the participation is voluntary, that participation can cease at any time, and that the session will be videotaped but their privacy of identification will be ensured.

The facilitator explained to the participants that the amount of time taken to complete the test task will be measured and that exploratory behavior outside the task flow should not occur until after task completion. The facilitator also instructed the participant to 'think aloud' so that a verbal record exists of their interaction with the unified media player prototype. The facilitator observed and entered user behavior, user comments, and system actions in the data logging application (usability data logger 5.1.1 – a screenshot of tasks list is in Appendix 3).¹

After each task, participants completed a post-task questionnaire (NASA-TLX). After all task scenarios were carried out, the participants completed a post-test satisfaction questionnaire (SUS) and answered the post-session short interview.

Participants

Fourteen participants comprising 4 researchers, 5 educators, and 5 users from the general public who have used audio visual media for varying needs or at least are familiar with Europeana evaluated the interactive version of the EUPS wireframe.

All the participants were found through snowball sampling, that is, personal networking and recruited through purposive sampling, that is, they were either familiar with Europeana portal or were using videos for varying needs suitable to the their user groups tasks. The basis for selection of participants was their availability, willingness to participate without any gift or monetary incentives, and professional use of, and experience with videos. However, all the participants from educators and general public user groups were compensated a gift voucher worth 50€ to spend on www.bol.com for their time.

The Tables below are the participants' their profiles and experiences.

Table 1: Audience Type

Educators	5
Researchers	4
General Public	5
Total (participants)	14

Table 2: Age

20 – 25	1
26 – 30	2
31 – 35	2
36 – 40	1
41 – 45	4
46 – 50	2
51 – 55	1
56 – 60	1
Total (participants)	14

¹ Usability datalogger is a free open source MS Excel application developed by Todd Zazelenchuk, Ph.D.

Table 3: Experience

Less than one year	0
>one year<5years	0
5 years	0
>5years<10years	5
10 years	2
More than 10 years	7
Total (participants)	14

Tasks Presentation and Analysis

Following is a summary of the participants' testing environment:

Table 4: Overview of computing environment

URLs of tested wireframes:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General public https://6bxu7z.axshare.com 2. Educators - https://cjf0ky.axshare.com 3. Researchers - https://xgul2p.axshare.com
Computer platforms:	Dell Latitude 5480 Intel Core i5-6300U CPU with a 14" display
Browser used:	Mozilla Firefox, Internet Explorer (for pre-test questionnaire)
Screen resolution:	1920 X 1080
Operating system:	Windows 10
Connection type:	Wired

Data logger 5 MS Excel tool was used as the usability logging tool by the facilitator and an observer (for the tests in Leuven). The sessions were video recorded using a Samsung smartphone. The room was set up such that there is a desk for the test participant, a desk for the facilitator and another desk for the observer. The facilitator mirrored the screen of the test participant to his laptop screen using the OBS studio app and AJA HDMI/USB 3 connectors. The recordings were done on the facilitator's official laptop. The test participant's screen was extended to a 15" Dell monitor for the observer and another official laptop was used by the observer for data logging.

Introductory Questions

Participants filled an online Google form questionnaire asking about their backgrounds, experience with videos, and their expectations for accessing videos online before they performed the tasks assigned to them. Table 5 and Figures 1-6 show their experiences, and expectations.

Table 5: Platforms used

Europeana	2
Vimeo	8
YouTube	14
TIB AV Portal	1
Others	12

Others* include Stream, Mediasite, Hp5, Daily Motion, VRT NU, Steven Spielberg Holocaust Film Archive, Filmothek (Bundesarchiv), Internet Archive, Amazon Prime, Netflix, AVA and Filmfriend. **This was a multiple choice question and answered by 14 participants.

Figure 1: Frequency of use of platforms (14 participants)

Figure 2: What participants like about media player on the platforms used (14 participants)

Note: This is an analysis of responses provided by all the 14 participants to a multiple choice question. Participants also indicated 'other' liked aspects and these include a lot of content, TED, easy to link to and share via social media, and embed video for blog.

Figure 3: Information support users desired (14 participants)

Note: This is an analysis of responses provided by all the 14 participants to an open-ended question.

Figure 4: Features contributing to users' positive experience (14 participants)

Note: This is an analysis of responses provided by all the 14 participants to an open-ended question.

Figure 5: Features used on users' platforms (14 participants)

Note: This is an analysis of responses provided by all the 14 participants to a multiple choice question. Participants also shared 'other' features used and these include quizzes, chapters and playback speed.

Figure 6: What users expected from an ideal platform for a media player (14 participants)

Note: This is an analysis of responses provided by all the 14 participants to an open-ended question.

Overall all the participants have been using different platforms and majorly YouTube to access videos for varying reasons and expect their ideal platform to support basic functionalities such as video annotation, subtitling, searching, chaptering, and downloading videos among others.

Findings and Recommendations

The participants were presented with three user stories with set of representative task scenarios and were asked to complete same as efficient, effective and satisfactory as possible, and to provide feedback afterwards. The participants expressed their thoughts aloud while going through the tasks. The following tasks were presented to the participants according to their user groups.

Table 6: Participants tasks list

#	Task	User group
1	Embed a video to a third-party platform	All
2	Subtitle a video	All
3	Export bibliographic metadata of a video	Researchers only
4	Share a video to Twitter	General public only
5	Check copyright information	All
6	Annotate a video	All
7	Preview annotated video on Europeana item page	All
8	Use a wizard to create a playlist	All
9	Edit a playlist in the video editor	All

Video Embed

The following issues were identified from user task efforts and assistance came from the facilitator in some cases.

Table 7: Embed video - issues seen

#	Task (Video Embed)
1	Many participants right clicked on the video and expected to see the option to embed a video. The facilitator had to inform that this option is not supported by the unified media player.
2	The share button on the video was not functional in the wireframe presented and was redundant for participants. The facilitator had to let participants know there was a share button elsewhere to work with.
3	Some participants confused embed code with share link.
4	Many participants were right clicking the embed code and copying it and ignoring the copy button they were supposed to click in order to copy the code.

Figure 7: Screenshots from video embed task

Video Subtitling

The following issues were identified from user task efforts and assistance came from the facilitator in some cases.

Table 8: Subtitle video - issues seen

#	Task (Video Subtitling)
1	The “plus sign (+) button for adding/saving new subtitles is not intuitive enough for many of the participants. The facilitator gave hints sometimes to the participants.
2	Some participants expected to see auto generation button for automatically generated subtitles.
3	A participant wanted to preview her subtitles before publishing them.
4	Some participants expected the “finalize” button to be placed in the bottom to avoid scrolling up and down.

Finalize, and subtitle addition/save buttons need to be reviewed and the redundant subtitle button on the player needs to be removed.

Figure 8: Screenshot from subtitle task

Video Annotation

The following issues were identified from user task efforts and assistance came from the facilitator in some cases.

Table 9: Annotate video and preview issues seen

#	Task (Video Subtitling)
1	The “plus sign (+) button is expected to launch the text box for writing annotations but was not implemented in the wireframe.
2	The delete icon button was not big enough for most of the participants to see and participants didn't use it as the option to delete annotations from the timeline.
3	The text edit icon was not visible to participants and colour contrast was poor.
4	The annotation type labels were redundant.
5	The “publish” button was not perceived as a button.
6	Most of the participants clicked and right clicked on an annotation in the timeline and expected to delete it.
7	Most of the participants confused the full screen button with large view button and were frustrated.
8	Most of the participants wanted redundant buttons to be hidden from the video player.
9	Most of the participants expected all essential and control buttons of the player to be placed bottom right of the video.
10	The “do more” button needs to contrast well with the video background.

Full screen button is redundant. Delete and edit icons are not visible enough and the “plus” button is not intuitive enough

9(A)

Annotation labels are redundant. Publish button was not perceived as a button and users wanted to delete annotations directly from the timeline.

9(B)

Users wanted buttons not needed for the task to be hidden and all controls and needed buttons to be placed bottom right of the video

9(C)

Figure 9: Screenshots from video annotation tasks

Video Playlist

The following issues were identified from user task efforts and assistance came from the facilitator in some cases.

This Share button was not part of the Europeana search results but was invented for the video playlist task. The button only appears when user selects more than one video to create into a playlist and users find the button easily.

10(A)

The playlist wizard (also invented for the usability test) was intuitive for users.

10(B)

The text edit icon was not visible to users and colour contrast was poor

The create button was not perceived as a button.

10(C)

Export button needs to be a "Copy" button and playlist code needs to be a code and not a platform selection.

10(D)

Figure 10: Screenshots from video playlist task

Item Page Issues

The following issues were identified from user task efforts and assistance came from the facilitator in some cases.

Participants right clicked on the video expecting to see an option to embed the video

View video was a link presented to help participants get to the video item page but the message was not instructive enough. Participants expect a message like "Click to see video details"

The copyright label button was appreciated but not large enough for participants to see. The copyright information was expected to stay for as long as participants wanted.

Figure 11: View video and copyright button/link

The copyright label button was appreciated but not large enough for participants to see. The copyright information was expected to stay for as long as participants wanted.

Figure 12: Copyright information disappears too quickly

Part of the export metadata wizard was hidden and user had to scroll down.

Figure 13: Bibliographic metadata export wizard is hidden partly down the item page

Performance Metrics

This section is the overview of the performance data metrics captured and brief explanations of each metric.

Task Complete Rate

All the five participants from the general public user group completed five tasks without any assistance as can be seen in Figure 14. Four participants completed embed and subtitle tasks without receiving assistance. One participant per each task was assisted. Two participants completed the video annotation and preview tasks, and three participants received some assistance. Assistance means telling the participants what to do, for example, clicking a button, when they get stuck to proceed with a task.

Figure 14: Task completion rate by general public

All the five participants in the educator user group completed five tasks without any assistance as can be seen in Figure 15. Nevertheless, there were observable levels of difficulties for completing embed, subtitle, and annotation tasks. Four participants each completed embed and subtitle tasks. There was a little technical error. The first participant from the educator group was wrongly presented with a page meant for the playlist task. As a result, and in order not to disrupt the session, both embed and subtitle tasks for this participant were not performed. The error came as a result of changing URLs for the different user group participants. There was a short time to prepare the test for this participant as he was a conference participant and came earlier than scheduled. Nevertheless, the error has no significant impact on the overall results both for the educator user group and generally.

Figure 15: Task completion rate by educators

All the four participants from the researcher user group completed five tasks without any assistance as can be seen in Figure 16. Two participants completed embed and annotation creation tasks without receiving assistance and two participants each got some assistance regarding the completion of the two tasks. Only one participant completed the video annotation preview task, and three participants were assisted. The assistance was mainly with finding the large view button.

Figure 16: Task completion rate by researchers

Task Complete Time

All 5 participants from the general public user group took a mean time of 300 seconds to complete embed, and annotation tasks as can be seen in Figure 17. Share, copyright, and playlist took lesser time to complete for this user group.

Figure 17: Task completion time by general public

All 5 participants from the educator user group also took a mean time of 300 seconds to complete the annotation creation task, as can be seen in Figure 18. Similarly, four participants took a mean time of 300 seconds to complete the video embed task. Video subtitling took a mean time of 150 seconds and copyright and playlist took lesser time to complete for this user group.

Figure 18: Task completion time by educators

All 4 participants from the researcher user group took a mean time of 300 seconds to complete embed, subtitle, and annotation tasks, as can be seen in Figure 19. Bibliographic metadata export to a mean time of 175 seconds, and copyright and playlist took lesser time to complete for this user group.

Figure 19: Task completion time by researchers

Above all, the time spent by the 14 participants in exploring and trying to find a button or understand them contributed to spending more time on one task than another. In some cases, participants had to be assisted when they get stuck, in effect contributing to the total time spent on such a task. The time spent on a task was tracked by the data logging application.

Problem Severity

Problem severity were treated as a combination of two factors –

1. The impact of the problem and;
2. The frequency of users experiencing the problem during the evaluation.

Impact

Impact is the ranking of the consequences of the problem by defining the level of impact that the problem has on successful task completion. There are three levels of impact:

- High - prevents the user from completing the task (critical error)
- Moderate - causes user difficulty but the task can be completed (non-critical error)
- Low - minor problems that do not significantly affect the task completion (non-critical error)

Frequency

Frequency is the percentage of participants who experience the problem when working on a task.

- High: 60% or more of the participants experience the problem
- Moderate: 21% - 59% of participants experience the problem
- Low: 20% or fewer of the participants experience the problem

Problem Severity Classification

The identified severity for each problem implies a general reward for resolving it, and a general risk for not addressing it, in the current release.

Severity 1

These are high impact problems that often prevent a user from correctly completing a task. They occur in varying frequency and are characteristic of calls to the Help Desk. Reward for resolution is typically exhibited in fewer Help Desk calls and reduced redevelopment costs.

Severity 2

Moderate to high frequency problems with moderate to low impact are typical of erroneous actions that the participant recognizes needs to be undone. Reward for resolution is typically exhibited in reduced time on task and decreased training costs.

Severity 3

Either moderate problems with low frequency or low problems with moderate frequency; these are minor annoyance problems faced by a number of participants. Reward for resolution is typically exhibited in reduced time on task and increased data integrity.

Severity 4

Low impact problems faced by few participants; there is low risk to not resolving these problems. Reward for resolution is typically exhibited in increased user satisfaction.

As can be seen in Figures 14-16, all participants from the three user groups completed at least five tasks without being assisted. Table 10 is a summary of problem severity assessments. The table indicates that most of the problems experienced by a few of the participants were moderate or a moderate percent of the participants experienced few problems. The problem mainly experienced with video embed is the confusion between share link and embed code, and the lack of affordance of the copy button to copy embed code for educators and researchers test participants. The problem with annotation creation is that participant struggled with the option provided to delete an annotation in the timeline. Participants also struggled with transitioning between the default preview mode and large view mode when previewing created annotations on the item page.

Table 10: Problem severity assessment

Tasks	General Users	Educators	Researchers
Embed	Severity 3	Severity 2	Severity 2
Subtitle	Severity 3	Severity 3	Severity 3
Export/Share	Severity 4	N/A	Severity 4
Annotate	Severity 2	Severity 2	Severity 2
Preview Annotations	Severity 3	Severity 3	Severity 2
Copyright	Severity 3	Severity 3	Severity 3
Create a playlist	Severity 3	Severity 3	Severity 3
Edit a playlist	Severity 3	Severity 3	Severity 3

Keys

- Severity 1 – High impact problems that prevents a user from completing a task.
- Severity 2 – Moderate to high frequency problems with low impact

- Severity 3 – Either moderate problem with low frequency or low problem with moderate frequency (minor).
- Severity 4 – Low impact problems faced by few users (very minor problems).

Task Level Satisfaction

All the scorings are from 0 to 100. The chart in Figure 20A is the average scoring per task factor workload by all the participants in a user group. The workload factors are explained in Appendix 4. The general public participants indicated they experienced a higher frustration level with annotation creation task compared to other tasks. They also required higher effort, performance, and mental demand to complete the annotation task compared to other tasks. The details are in Figure 20A. As shown in Figure 20B, putting all the six factors together and averaging them, the general public user group participants indicated annotation creation task made the most cognitive workload demand on them..

Figure 20A: Tasks cognitive records for general public user group

Figure 20B: Tasks average workloads for general public user group

The educator user group participants indicated they required more effort and mental demand to embed and annotate videos compared to other tasks. The details are in Figure 21A. As shown in Figure 21B on the average, the educator user group participants indicated annotation creation and embed tasks made the most cognitive workload demand on them.

Figure 21A: Tasks cognitive records for educator user group

Figure 21B: Tasks average workloads for educator user group

The researcher user group participants indicated they required more effort, performance, and mental demand to work on video annotation, embed, and subtitle tasks compared to other tasks. The details are in Figure 22A. As

shown in Figure 22B, the researcher user group participants indicated video subtitling, embed, and annotation tasks on the average made the most cognitive workload demand on them.

Figure 22A: Tasks cognitive records for researcher user group

Figure 22B: Tasks average workloads for researcher user group

Overall, on the average, all of the tasks workload demands are below 50% for all the user groups. Nevertheless, there were few cases where annotation creation task made more than 50% of mental, effort, and performance demands on both the general public, and educator user groups. Similarly, embed and subtitle creation tasks made more than 50% of mental, effort, and performance demands on both the educator and researcher user groups.

Overall System Satisfaction

The average system usability assessment score by the general public user group is 62% as shown in Figure 23. The highest score is 85% and the lowest is 35%.

Figure 23: System usability assessment by the general public user group

The average system usability assessment score by the educator user group is 46% as shown in Figure 24. The highest score is 87.5% and the lowest is 15%.

Figure 24: System usability assessment by the educator user group

The average system usability assessment score by the researcher user group is 63% as shown in Figure 25. The highest score is 80% and the lowest is 27.5%.

Figure 25: System usability assessment by the researcher user group

Overall, as can be seen in Figure 26, the average score is 57%. The level of experience, enthusiasm, and expectations of the participants all contributed to their judgments. The average grade by the participants for the unified media player is C.

Figure 26: Overall users' satisfaction²

It should be noted however, that the participants evaluated both the unified player and the editor. Therefore, the scoring and grading should be perceived as being holistic for both the media player and video editor.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made in view of the findings:

Table 11: problems encountered by participants and recommendations

Supporting Evidence	Recommendations	What is Affected?
<p>Annotation preview <i>"I would like to view this video in large view and I clicked on the two arrow icon on the right but it won't" (large view button) – Gen_2</i> <i>"It is understandable but I didn't see it; on YouTube it is down" (large view button) – Edu_5</i> <i>"The one that I would usually use (full screen button) doesn't work" (confusion with large view button) "I found it but it looks strange" – Gen_3</i> <i>"I don't seem to get to the (large view mode)... I don't know the only option I see is these two arrows(full screen button) and when I click on it, nothing seems to happen " – Res_3</i> <i>"My advice is; make it simple with less functionality. The</i></p>	<p><i>Remove redundant icons/buttons on the unified player.</i> <i>Present only required icons/buttons/labels necessary for a task and hide those not needed.</i> <i>Reposition player control icons/buttons to bottom of the player mostly to the right.</i> <i>Place the default/large view buttons to the bottom right of the player.</i></p>	<p><i>Unified media player</i></p>

² The original chart was retrieved from <https://measuringu.com/interpret-sus-score/>

problem is when there is too much functionalities you can't find anything" – Edu_1
"I tried this (full screen button) but it didn't react". I expect this information... it is not on the left-side, it is usually on the right below" – Res_4

Copying embed code

"That is not a button for me" (copy button for embed code, "this is not like a button. A button for me is with a frame" publish button in the editor) – Edu_5

"I would not actually think (it is a button), because it is not highlighted in colour, not big..." (copy button for embed code) – Res_3

Labels above icons/buttons

I am just confused because there are icons on the left and icons in the bottom... instead of the three dots you can say "do more" or annotate, pen-symbol, " – Res_3

"I have difficulty finding the do more button, identifying this button" – Res_4

Buttons positioning

"I would expect to finalize under because I have been working on the left side (suggests the "finalize button should be in the bottom) – Res_3

Annotation creation buttons

"It is very invisible to my eyes" (editable button above text box) – Edu_3

The colour looks a bit funny, like a glitch on the page" (editable button above text box) – Res_3

"How am I supposed to know what to do?" (trash bin delete icon) – Edu_3

„I don't really know how to delete it" Gen_2

Redesign the embed code "copy" button, publish button in editor, create button in the editor. Place the copy button beside the embed code as illustrated below:

```
<iframe lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenen euismod Bibendum laoreet></iframe> Copy
```

Add text labels above interactive icons/buttons. See an example below:

To ensure all functionalities and interactivity are around the media player and the editor, interactive buttons should be strategically-positioned. For example, if a user starts a task from the top and the task ends in the bottom of the page, the finalize button should be in the bottom. Users get frustrated scrolling up and down the page.

Some buttons such as trash bin icon for deleting annotations and editable icon above the text box after typing and saving texts should be redesigned / enlarged.

Use a button label "Delete" as shown below to replace the trash bin icon.

Delete

Item page on Europeana

Unified media player

Unified media player and Video editor

Video editor

<p>Button redesign <i>"This is not a button. Blue means there is a link behind it. I am copying not exporting" – Edu_5</i></p>	<p><i>Review the playlist workflow process and the buttons (save/cancel, create, copy playlist code). See illustrations below:</i></p>	<p><i>Video editor</i></p>
<p>Previewing the video in the editor before publishing <i>"I would expect to preview. One is afraid of publishing something one has not previewed yet" – Res_4</i></p>	<p><i>Review the subtitle workflow process and the buttons</i></p>	<p><i>Video editor</i></p>
<p>Downloading annotations with video <i>"This is the download button but it doesn't work" (download button on the player in playing mode) – Edu_1</i> <i>"I clicked download but nothing happens" – Res_4</i></p>	<p><i>Should be possible to download annotated video from the item page.</i></p>	<p><i>Item page on Europeana</i></p>
<p>Auto-generated subtitles <i>"Many subtitles are already in the net and would be nice to have a tool that finds the subtitles already available in the net" - Res_4</i></p>	<p><i>Should be possible to reuse already created subtitles for the same video.</i></p>	<p><i>Video editor</i></p>
<p>Copyright button on the result item page <i>"Where is the copyright information?" – Res_2</i> <i>"Is this the copyright?" – Res_1</i> <i>"There is a small copyright sign" – Edu_2</i> <i>"What bothers me is that I have to re-click before I read it, it doesn't stay there, I would prefer to make it like a hover, so when my mouse is over the copyright it stays hook all the time" – Edu_2</i></p>	<p><i>Enlarge the copyright information label/button and make the copyright information visible by ensuring a click on the button/label and hidden by a second click (first click -> shows copyright information and second click -> hides copyright information) on the results item page.</i></p>	<p><i>Item page on Europeana</i></p>
<p>Short text linking to item page <i>"Where is the detail page?" – Res_3</i></p>	<p><i>Add a short description (click to see video details) with a link to the video item page from the search results page</i></p>	<p><i>Item page on Europeana</i></p>
<p>Options for deleting annotations in editing mode</p>	<p><i>Should be possible to delete annotations directly from the timeline before finalizing.</i></p>	<p><i>Video editor</i></p>

<p>„I don't really know how to delete it“ Gen_2 “How am I supposed to know what to do?” (trash bin delete icon) – Edu_3 „I wanna click here“ (annotation in the timeline) – Res_3 Do More button on the player “It is hard to know the three dots because of the paintings behind”(Do more button) – Edu_3 “I didn't perceive this as a subtitle button because I am used to some icons” – Res_4</p>	<p>Unified media player</p>
<p>Ensure the “do more” button contrasts well with the video. Add a label “Do more” above the do more button OR a droplist of features such that when the button can be clicked and user can choose specific feature e.g. embed, annotate, playlist, subtitle</p>	

Post-test Interview

At the end of each session, we asked participants nine questions:

1. What are your overall impressions of the media player?
2. If you have to give the media player a grade, from A to F, where A was exemplary and F was failing, what grade would you give it and why?
3. What are the three things you like best about the unified media player?
4. What are the three things you like least about the unified media player?
5. If you could make one significant change to this unified media player, what change would you make?
6. Would you return to use this unified media player on europeana.eu on your own in the future? Why/why not?
7. Are there features you would like to see added to the unified media player? Which ones?
8. Would you recommend this europeana.eu media player to a colleague? To a friend?
9. Do you have any other questions or comments about the media player or your experiences with it?

The following is the summary of participants' responses to the post-test interview questions:

1. Nearly all the participants liked the features presented.
2. On the average participants gave a grade “C” to the media player. Some were excited with features, simplicity of the interface and colour alignment, while some were frustrated with non-functional buttons presented.
3. On the average participants liked the fact the “do more” button and concept is consistent with other known interactive systems, features such as annotation, subtitle, embed and playlist are nice, as well as the adequacy and reliability of contents to encourage re-use.

4. Nevertheless, the three least liked things about the media player: arrangement/positioning of some buttons/icons and or their lack of visibility, limited option to delete an annotation, and lack of intuitiveness especially due to absence of labels on top of functional buttons/icons, lack of hints and or short tutorials.
5. Elements on the item pages and media player should be more intuitive to interact with. Minimalistic design is essential (simple to use) with short descriptions of icons, buttons, links and labels.
6. Most of the participants would return to use the media player for their professional work support.
7. Additional features/enhancement suggested includes: video transcript, adding more information to video metadata, end screen comment or URL, video chapters, clipping, video cataloguing, video library, 10s >>/<<, language versions for the features and processes, Geo-location information, Cross-referencing citation information, and number of views.
8. Most of the participants are also willing to recommend the media player to their friends and colleagues if the media player is relevant to their needs.
9. Most can't wait to use the media player and asked when they should expect to see the unified media player on Europeana.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are reached based on the usability evaluation questions raised:

1. To a medium extent the interaction architecture and design of the unified media player are comprehensible to users.
2. The different user groups could solve typical usage tasks to a medium satisfaction level.
3. The learning curve of the media player appears not steep for the majority. With the improvements as recommended, most users could learn to use the media player and editor quickly.
4. Few buttons and icons such as large view mode button, copy button (for embed) are not clearly understood by the majority of the users. These should be redesigned or repositioned.
5. To a large extent users can find all the information they need in the unified player. However, few suggestions were made.

Appendix 1: Usability evaluation tasks

Usability tasks

Educator user group

View, embed and subtitle a video

A teacher, Petra, is visiting the Europeana website searching for footage on the fall of Berlin wall to use it in a history lesson titled “Germany in the 1980s” she is preparing for her class on a third-party platform. She finds a nice short video (the wall blown up) on Europeana but it’s in German. She decides to use that clip even if most of her students only know English. From the Europeana item page, she clicks to view the video (the wall blown up). She reads the copyright information to know what she is allowed to do with the selected video. In this case, the content owner of the video, INA, allows users like Petra to reuse the video. Petra sees and clicks a share button on the item page. She clicks the embed icon that, like on YouTube, generates an embed code she can paste in her third-party platform learning environment. Petra then clicks the copy button to copy the embed code to her own lesson page on the third-party platform. She updates the contents and inspects the video clip. She sees a “do more...” button, which she clicks and then creates subtitles to the video in English in the Europeana unified player editor. Petra saves the subtitles and clicks the publish button to finalise her work in the third-party platform. Petra displays the subtitle video in the third-party platform to verify that everything was well-done. The students who will access the third-party platform lesson with the embedded video will see the edited version.

Expected steps to take:

-
- Step 1: Petra checks the select button besides a video (the wall blown up) on Europeana.
 - Step 2: Petra clicks the “share” button on the Europeana unified player item page.
 - Step 3: Petra clicks the embed icon on the embed wizard.
 - Step 4: Petra clicks the copy button on the embed wizard
 - Step 5: Petra pastes the embed code in her third-party platform
 - Step 6: Petra previews the video in the third-party platform editor by clicking the “update” button.
 - Step 7: Petra clicks the “do more button” on the previewing video in the third-party platform.
 - Step 8: Petra clicks the “create new subtitle” button in the Europeana video editor.
 - Step 9: Petra selects English from the select language drop list.
 - Step 10: Petra checks the “pause video while typing” box.
 - Step 11: Petra drags the timeline slider to the desired part on the video.
 - Step 12: Petra types the subtitles in the text window.
 - Step 13: Petra clicks the “plus-sign” button below the text window to save the subtitle.
 - Step 14: Petra clicks the “publish” button.
 - Step 15: Petra clicks the “finalize” button.
 - Step 16: Petra clicks the “OK” option.
 - Step 17: Petra clicks the “save and display” button in her third-party platform.

Browse and annotate a video

Petra is preparing another video she found on Europeana for a history lesson. Petra views the video titled “the ancient painting” on Europeana unified player. Petra finds a button to do more where she could annotate the video in the Europeana unified player editor. Petra clicks the “do more” button and begins to annotate the video by selecting the appropriate annotation type and creating the annotations. Petra would like to use the text “Lorem” to annotate “speech in the video”. Petra saves the speech annotation text. She sees a small icon above and at the edge of the text window, which allows her to edit his annotations or type new ones. Alternatively, Petra could also use a “plus-sign button” on the editor to create a new annotation. Petra selects “image in the video” and types and saves the text “Ipsum lorem”. Finally, she types the text “Lorem lorem” to annotate a “text in the video” and saves. Petra publishes to see the annotations. However, before finalizing and downloading the annotated video, she thought of deleting one of the annotations (“Lorem”) from the timeline. Petra downloads the annotated video and would upload it later to a third-party platform. Petra has now finalized her annotations, but she decides to view them on the Europeana unified player. She toggles the buttons and in particular clicked to see the annotations timelines both in the default view and large (not full screen) view modes. She moves her mouse over the annotations in the timelines to see the various annotation types. She also clicks on them to see specific parts of the video. In the large view mode, Petra sees a “plus-sign” button, which allows her to see and hide the annotations. Petra could also vertically scroll through the annotations timelines. Finally, Petra could click the subtitle button to view and hide the subtitles.

Expected steps to take:

-
- Step 1: Petra clicks and views a video (the ancient painting) on Europeana item page.
 - Step 2: Petra hovers and clicks the “do more” button on the unified player.
 - Step 3: Petra clicks the “plus-sign” button in the unified player editor.
 - Step 4: Petra selects an annotation type.
 - Step 5: Petra types in the text box.
 - Step 6: Petra clicks the “save” button below the text box or cancel to repeat step 12.
 - Step 7: Petra repeats steps 10 – 13 for the different annotation types.
 - Step 8: Petra clicks the “publish” button.
 - Step 9: Petra selects an annotation “lorem”.
 - Step 10: Petra observes the selected annotation greyed out on the timeline.
 - Step 11: Petra click the “delete” icon.
 - Step 12: Petra verifies the selected and greyed out annotation was deleted from the timeline.
 - Step 13: Petra clicks the “download annotated video” button in the video editor.
 - Step 14: Petra clicks the “Finalize” button in the video editor.
 - Step 15: Petra clicks the “OK” button that appears in the video editor.
 - Step 16: Petra hovers the annotation in the default screen.
 - Step 17: Petra scrolls up and down to see the timelines in the default view.
 - Step 18: Petra clicks on the annotations to see specific parts of the video.
 - Step 19: Petra clicks the “subtitle” button to view and hide the video subtitles.
 - Step 20: Petra clicks the “large view screen” button (not full screen).
 - Step 21: Petra repeats steps 16 – 19.
 - Step 22: Petra the “default view screen” button to go back to the default view.

Browse and create a playlist

Petra is also a blogger. She uses her blog posts to educate young adults and share something interesting with her colleagues. Petra is preparing her next blog post on the fall of the Berlin wall. She is using various online sources to gather relevant information, including the Europeana Collections portal, where she heard there is quite a number of interesting footage on Berlin wall from broadcasters' archives across Europe. She has searched for video contents on the "Berlin wall" on Europeana, and now is browsing through the search results. Petra checks the copyright information and watches some interesting clips and selects 4 videos namely:

- the wall is open
- the fall of Berlin wall
- Berlin after the wall fall
- the former border strip

Now Petra would like to "copy" this playlist to her blog platform. She simply clicks on the "share" button that appears after selecting a video from the search results and follows a pop-up wizard window that comes out, asking first if she wants to share the selected videos. Petra opts to create a video playlist and a playlist code is generated on the fly to the Europeana video editor manager. Petra names her playlist as "The fall of the Berlin wall". Petra selects her platform (platform 2) to copy the playlist code to and pastes the code in her platform editor. Petra previews the playlist and finally, publishes her new blog post and verified the playlist was inserted.

Expected steps to take:

-
- Step 1: Petra checks the copyright information and watches some interesting clips.
 - Step 2: Petra selects 4 videos namely:
 - the wall is open
 - the fall of Berlin wall
 - Berlin wall after the fall
 - the former border strip
 - Step 3: Petra clicks on the "share" button that appears after selecting a video from the search result on the item page.
 - Step 4: Petra clicks the "create a playlist of selected videos" radio button on the playlist wizard.
 - Step 5: Petra types the name "The fall of the Berlin wall".
 - Step 6: Petra clicks the "save" button below the text window or the "cancel" button to repeat step 5.
 - Step 7: Petra clicks the "create" button.
 - Step 8: Petra selects "platform 2" from the drop list to copy the playlist code to.
 - Step 9: Petra clicks the "export" button.
 - Step 10: Petra clicks the "finalize" button.
 - Step 11: Petra clicks the "OK" button.
 - Step 12: Petra pastes the code in his platform editor.
 - Step 13: Petra clicks the "preview" button.
 - Step 14: Petra clicks the "publish" button to publish her new blog post and verified the playlist was inserted.

Researcher user group

View, embed and subtitle a video

Sam Ethnologist, lectures in a university and teaches a course “Ancient and modern Europe”. Sam is visiting the Europeana website searching for footage on the Berlin wall to use it in a lesson he is preparing for his class on a third-party platform. He finds a nice short video (the wall blown up) on Europeana but it’s in German. He decides to use that clip even if most of his students only know English. From the Europeana item page, he clicks to view the video (the wall blown up). He reads the copyright information to know what he is allowed to do with the selected video. In this case, the content owner of the video, INA, allows users like Sam to reuse the video. Sam sees and clicks a share button on the item page. He clicks the embed icon that, like on YouTube, generates an embed code he can paste in his third-party platform learning environment. Sam then clicks the copy button to copy the embed code to his own lesson page on the third-party platform. He updates the contents and inspects the video clip. He sees a “do more...” button, which he clicks and then creates subtitles to the video in English. He saves the subtitles and clicks the publish button to finalise his work in the third-party platform. Sam displays the subtitle video in the third-party platform to verify that everything was well-done. The students who will access the third-party platform lesson with the embedded video will see the edited version.

Expected steps to take:

-
- | | |
|----------|--|
| Embed | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Step 1: Sam checks the select button besides a video (the wall blown up) on Europeana.• Step 2: Sam clicks the “share” button on the Europeana unified player item page.• Step 3: Sam clicks the embed icon on the embed wizard.• Step 4: Sam clicks the copy button on the embed wizard• Step 5: Sam pastes the embed code in his third-party platform |
| Subtitle | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Step 6: Sam previews the video in the third-party platform editor by clicking the “update” button.• Step 7: Sam clicks the “do more button” on the previewing video in the third-party platform.• Step 8: Sam clicks the “create new subtitle” button in the Europeana video editor.• Step 9: Sam selects English from the select language drop list.• Step 10: Sam checks the “pause video while typing” box.• Step 11: Sam drags the timeline slider to the desired part on the video.• Step 12: Sam types the subtitles in the text window.• Step 13: Sam clicks the “plus-sign” button below the text window to save the subtitle.• Step 14: Sam clicks the “publish” button.• Step 15: Sam clicks the “finalize” button.• Step 16: Sam clicks the “OK” option.• Step 17: Sam clicks the “save and display” button in his third-party platform. |

Browse, export metadata and annotate a video

Sam is preparing for a new journal article to be published in viewjournal.eu. First, he wants to look for relevant videos on Europeana which demonstrate carving used in religious contexts. Sam clicks to view a video titled “the ancient painting” on Europeana unified player. Sam wants to view the copyright information and bibliographic metadata of the video and export the metadata and the DOI of the video to the Zotero referencing manager. First, Sam reads the metadata and exports them to his desktop. He would upload later to viewjournal.eu from his desktop. Furthermore, Sam inspects the video and finds a button to do more where he could annotate the video in

Europeana unified player editor. Sam clicks the “do more” button and begins to annotate the video by selecting the appropriate annotation type and creating the annotations. Sam would like to use the text "Lorem" to annotate "speech in the video". Sam saves the speech annotation text. He sees a small icon above and at the edge of the text window, which allows him to edit his annotations or type new ones. Alternatively, Sam could also click a “plus-sign button” on the editor to create a new annotation. Sam selects "image in the video" types and saves the text “Ipsum lorem”. Finally, he types the text "Lorem lorem” to annotate a "text in the video" and saves. Summary of Sam’s annotations in the Europeana video manager editor (the annotation texts and types are: speech in video – Lorem (time on video is 0.11), image in video – Ipsum lorem (0.37), and text in video – Lorem lorem (1.21)). Sam publishes to see the annotations. However, before finalizing and downloading the annotated video, he thought of deleting one of the annotations (“Lorem”) from the timeline. Sam downloads the annotated video and would upload it later to a third-party platform. Sam has now finalized his annotations, but he decides to view them on the Europeana unified player. He toggles the buttons and in particular clicked to see the annotations timelines both in the default view and large (not full screen) view modes. He moves his mouse over the annotations in the timelines to see the various annotation types. He also clicks on them to see specific parts of the video. In the large view mode, Sam sees a “plus-sign” button, which allows him to see and hide the annotations. Sam could also vertically scroll through the annotations timelines. Finally, Sam could click the subtitle button to view and hide the subtitles.

Expected steps to take:

- | | |
|---------------------|---|
| Annotate | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Sam clicks and views a video (the ancient painting) on Europeana item page. • Step 2: Sam reads the bibliographic metadata and DOIs of the video. • Step 3: Sam selects Zotero. • Step 4: Sam clicks the “export metadata” button. • Step 5: Sam clicks the “browse” button on the pop-up wizard. • Step 6: Sam clicks “desktop” save the metadata file to. • Step 7: Sam clicks the “OK” button to close the save destination window. • Step 8: Sam clicks the “OK” button to close the export metadata wizard. • Step 9: Sam hovers and clicks the “do more” button on the unified player. • Step 10: Sam clicks the “plus-sign” button in the unified player editor. • Step 11: Sam selects an annotation type. • Step 12: Sam types in the text box. • Step 13: Sam clicks the “save” button below the text box or cancel to repeat step 12. • Step 14: Sam repeats steps 10 – 13 for the different annotation types. • Step 15: Sam clicks the “publish” button. • Step 16: Sam selects an annotation “lorem”. • Step 17: Sam observes the selected annotation greyed out on the timeline. • Step 18: Sam click the “delete” icon. • Step 19: Sam verifies the selected and greyed out annotation was deleted from the timeline. |
| Preview Annotations | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 20: Sam clicks the “download annotated video” button in the video editor. • Step 21: Sam clicks the “Finalize” button in the video editor. • Step 22: Sam clicks the “OK” button that appears in the video editor. • Step 23: Sam hovers the annotation in the default screen. • Step 24: Sam scrolls up and down to see the timelines in the default view. • Step 25: Sam clicks on the annotations to see specific parts of the video. • Step 26: Sam clicks the “subtitle” button to view and hide the video subtitles. • Step 27: Sam clicks the “large view screen” button (not full screen). |

- Step 28: Sam repeats steps 23 – 26.
- Step 29: Sam the “default view screen” button to go back to the default view.

Browse and create a playlist

Sam is also a blogger. He uses his blog posts to share something interesting with his colleagues. Sam is preparing his next blog post on “The Fall of the Berlin Wall”. He is using various online sources to gather relevant information, including the Europeana Collections portal, where he heard there is quite a number of interesting footage on Berlin wall from broadcasters’ archives across Europe. Sam has searched for video contents on the “Berlin wall” on Europeana, and now is browsing through the search results. Sam checks the copyright information and watches some interesting clips and selects 4 videos namely:

- the wall is open
- the fall of Berlin wall
- Berlin after the wall fall
- the former border strip

Now Sam would like to “copy” this playlist to his blog platform. He simply clicks on the “share” button that appears after selecting a video from the search results and follows a pop-up wizard window that comes out, asking first if he wants to share the selected videos. Sam opts to create a video playlist and a playlist code is generated on the fly to the Europeana video editor manager. Sam names his playlist as “The fall of the Berlin wall”. Sam selects his platform (platform 2) to copy the playlist code to and pastes the code in his platform editor. Sam previews the playlist and finally, publishes his new blog post and verified the playlist was inserted.

General public

View, embed and subtitle a video

A Media Journalist, Aubery, is visiting the Europeana website searching for footage on the fall of Berlin wall to use it in a news report titled “Germany in the 1980s” she is preparing for her readers on a third-party platform. She finds a nice short video (the wall blown up) on Europeana but it’s in German. She decides to use that clip even if most of her readers only know English. From the Europeana item page, she clicks to view the video (the wall blown up). She reads the copyright information to know what she is allowed to do with the selected video. In this case, the content owner of the video, INA, allows users like Aubery to reuse the video. Aubery sees and clicks a share button on the item page. She clicks the embed icon that, like on YouTube, generates an embed code she can paste in her third-party platform learning environment. Aubery then clicks the copy button to copy the embed code to her own news item page on the third-party platform. She updates the contents and inspects the video clip. She sees a “do more...” button, which she clicks and then creates subtitles to the video in English in the Europeana unified player editor. Aubery saves the subtitles and clicks the publish button to finalise her work in the third-party platform. Aubery displays the subtitle video in the third-party platform to verify that everything was well-done. The readers who will access the third-party platform news item with the embedded video will see the edited version.

Expected steps to take:

-
- Step 1: Aubery checks the select button besides a video (the wall blown up) on Europeana.
 - Step 2: Aubery clicks the “share” button on the Europeana unified player item page.
 - Step 3: Aubery clicks the embed icon on the embed wizard.
 - Step 4: Aubery clicks the copy button on the embed wizard
 - Step 5: Aubery pastes the embed code in her third-party platform
 - Step 6: Aubery previews the video in the third-party platform editor by clicking the “update” button.
 - Step 7: Aubery clicks the “do more button” on the previewing video in the third-party platform.
 - Step 8: Aubery clicks the “create new subtitle” button in the Europeana video editor.
 - Step 9: Petra selects English from the select language drop list.
 - Step 10: Aubery checks the “pause video while typing” box.
 - Step 11: Aubery drags the timeline slider to the desired part on the video.
 - Step 12: Aubery types the subtitles in the text window.
 - Step 13: Aubery clicks the “plus-sign” button below the text window to save the subtitle.
 - Step 14: Aubery clicks the “publish” button.
 - Step 15: Aubery clicks the “finalize” button.
 - Step 16: Aubery clicks the “OK” option.
 - Step 17: Aubery clicks the “save and display” button in her third-party platform.

View, share and annotate a video

Aubery is preparing another video she found on Europeana for another news item. Aubery views the video titled “the ancient painting” on Europeana unified player. First, Aubery reads would like to share the video with his followers on Twitter. Furthermore, Aubery finds a button to do more where she could annotate the video in the Europeana unified player editor. Aubery clicks the “do more” button and begins to annotate the video by selecting

the appropriate annotation type and creating the annotations. Aubery would like to use the text "Lorem" to annotate "speech in the video". Aubery saves the speech annotation text. She sees a small icon above and at the edge of the text window, which allows her to edit his annotations or type new ones. Alternatively, Aubery could also use a "plus-sign button" on the editor to create a new annotation. Aubery selects "image in the video" and types and saves the text "Ipsum lorem". Finally, she types the text "Lorem lorem" to annotate a "text in the video" and saves. Aubery publishes to see the annotations. However, before finalizing and downloading the annotated video, she thought of deleting one of the annotations ("Lorem") from the timeline. Aubery downloads the annotated video and would upload it later to a third-party platform. Aubery has now finalized her annotations, but she decides to view them on the Europeana unified player. She toggles the buttons and in particular clicked to see the annotations timelines both in the default view and large (not full screen) view modes. She moves her mouse over the annotations in the timelines to see the various annotation types. She also clicks on them to see specific parts of the video. In the large view mode, Aubery sees a "plus-sign" button, which allows her to see and hide the annotations. Aubery could also vertically scroll through the annotations timelines. Finally, Aubery could click the subtitle button to view and hide the subtitles.

Expected steps to take:

- | | |
|---------------------|---|
| Annotate | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Aubery clicks and views a video (the ancient painting) on Europeana item page. • Step 2: Aubery clicks the "share" button on the Europeana item page. • Step 3: Aubery clicks the Twitter icon. • Step 4: Aubery finalizes her tweet and clicks the "Tweet" button. • Step 5: Aubery hovers and clicks the "do more" button on the unified player. • Step 6: Aubery clicks the "plus-sign" button in the unified player editor. • Step 7: Aubery selects an annotation type. • Step 8: Aubery types in the text box. • Step 9: Aubery clicks the "save" button below the text box or cancel to repeat step 12. • Step 10: Aubery repeats steps 10 – 13 for the different annotation types. • Step 11: Aubery clicks the "publish" button. • Step 12: Aubery selects an annotation "lorem". • Step 13: Aubery observes the selected annotation greyed out on the timeline. • Step 14: Aubery click the "delete" icon. • Step 15: Aubery verifies the selected and greyed out annotation was deleted from the timeline. |
| Preview Annotations | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 16: Aubery clicks the "download annotated video" button in the video editor. • Step 17: Aubery clicks the "Finalize" button in the video editor. • Step 18: Aubery clicks the "OK" button that appears in the video editor. • Step 19: Aubery hovers the annotation in the default screen. • Step 20: Aubery scrolls up and down to see the timelines in the default view. • Step 21: Aubery clicks on the annotations to see specific parts of the video. • Step 22: Aubery clicks the "subtitle" button to view and hide the video subtitles. • Step 23: Aubery clicks the "large view screen" button (not full screen). • Step 24: Aubery repeats steps 16 – 19. • Step 25: Aubery the "default view screen" button to go back to the default view. |

Browse and create a playlist

Aubery is also a blogger. She uses her blog posts to educate young adults and share something interesting with her colleagues. Aubery is preparing her next blog post on the fall of the Berlin wall. She is using various online sources to gather relevant information, including the Europeana Collections portal, where she heard there is quite a number of interesting footage on Berlin wall from broadcasters' archives across Europe. She has searched for video contents on the "Berlin wall" on Europeana, and now is browsing through the search results. Aubery checks the copyright information and watches some interesting clips and selects 4 videos namely:

- the wall is open
- the fall of Berlin wall
- Berlin after the wall fall
- the former border strip

Now Aubery would like to "copy" this playlist to her blog platform. She simply clicks on the "share" button that appears after selecting a video from the search results and follows a pop-up wizard window that comes out, asking first if she wants to share the selected videos. Aubery opts to create a video playlist and a playlist code is generated on the fly to the Europeana video editor manager. Aubery names her playlist as "The fall of the Berlin wall". Aubery selects her platform (platform 2) to copy the playlist code to and pastes the code in her platform editor. Aubery previews the playlist and finally, publishes her new blog post and verified the playlist was inserted.

Expected steps to take:

-
- Step 1: Aubery checks the copyright information and watches some interesting clips.
 - Step 2: Aubery selects 4 videos namely:
 - the wall is open
 - the fall of Berlin wall
 - Berlin wall after the fall
 - the former border strip
 - Step 3: Aubery clicks on the "share" button that appears after selecting a video from the search result on the item page.
 - Step 4: Aubery clicks the "create a playlist of selected videos" radio button on the playlist wizard.
 - Step 5: Aubery types the name "The fall of the Berlin wall".
 - Step 6: Aubery clicks the "save" button below the text window or the "cancel" button to repeat step 5.
 - Step 7: Aubery clicks the "create" button.
 - Step 8: Aubery selects "platform 2" from the drop list to copy the playlist code to.
 - Step 9: Aubery clicks the "export" button.
 - Step 10: Aubery clicks the "finalize" button.
 - Step 11: Aubery clicks the "OK" button.
 - Step 12: Aubery pastes the code in his platform editor.
 - Step 13: Aubery clicks the "preview" button.
 - Step 14: Aubery clicks the "publish" button to publish her new blog post and verified the playlist was inserted.

Appendix 2: Pre-test questionnaire

EUPS_Pre_Test_Questionnaire

Thank you for your time in completing this brief survey to help us to understand your experience with the use of videos.

Participant code *

1. Which web sites do you use to access videos? *

Please add others if necessary

Europeana

Vimeo

YouTube

TIB AV Portal

Other:

2. How often do you use these websites? *

Everyday in a week

One day in a week

Two days in a week

Three days in a week

Up to 4 days in a week

Up to 5 days in a week

Up to 6 days in week

3. What do you like about media player on the web sites you have used? *

Beautiful interface

Intuitiveness

Ease of use

Support to re-use a video professionally

Interactivity

Offline access

Other:

4. What do you dislike about media player on the web sites you have used?

5. What types of information or support do you look for in a media player? *

6. How long have you been using media player on online platforms or repositories?

- Less than one year
- More than one year but less than 5 years
- 5 years
- More than 5 years but less than 10 years
- 10 years
- More than 10 years

7. Do any of the media players you used have features to help make your experience positive? Explain briefly why? *

8. Which of these features have you used regarding videos? (Select all that applies)

- Annotation
- Embed
- Subtitle
- Playlist
- Metadata export
- Other:

9. If you were to envision your ideal platform for using media player, what sorts of information would it contain? How would it be organized? Explain briefly *

Never submit passwords through Google Forms.

Appendix 3: Data logger screenshot of educator user group tasks list

EUPS Usability Datalogger

Tasks
 Step 1: Enter tasks and indicate settings for each item.
 Step 2: Click **SAVE CHANGES** to see effect on P worksheets.

#	Task (aka_Scenario/Question)	Chart Label	Scored	TaskCards	Random
1	Embed a video	Embed	Yes	No	
2	Subtitle a video	Subtitle	Yes	No	
3	Share a video to Twitter	Share	No	No	
4	Annotate and download an annotated video	Annotate	Yes	No	
5	Preview an annotated video	Pre_annotat	Yes	No	
6	Check copyright information	Copyright	Yes	No	
7	Create a playlist using wizard	Playlist_wiz	Yes	No	
8	Finalise a playlist in Europeana video editor	Playlist_edi	Yes	No	
9			No	No	
10			No	No	
11			No	No	
12			No	No	
13			No	No	
14			No	No	
15			No	No	
16			No	No	
17			No	No	
18			No	No	
19			No	No	
20			No	No	
21			No	No	
22			No	No	
23			No	No	
24			No	No	
25			No	No	
26			No	No	
27			No	No	
28			No	No	
29			No	No	
30			No	No	
31			No	No	
32			No	No	

Appendix 4: Workload rating scale definitions according to NASA -TLX

Factor	Endpoints	Descriptions
Mental Demand	<i>Low/High</i>	How much mental and perceptual activity was required (e.g. thinking, deciding, calculating, remembering, looking, searching, etc.)? Was the task easy or demanding, simple or complex, exacting or forgiving?
Physical Demand	<i>Low/High</i>	How much physical activity was required? (e.g. pushing, pulling, turning, controlling, activating, etc.)? Was the task easy or demanding, slow or brisk, slack or strenuous, restful or laborious?
Temporal Demand	<i>Low/High</i>	How much time pressure did you feel due to the rate or pace at which the tasks or task elements occurred? Was the pace slow and leisurely or rapid and frantic?
Performance	<i>Good/Poor</i>	How successful do you think you were in accomplishing the goals of the task set by the experimenter (or yourself)? How satisfied were you with your performance in accomplishing these goals?
Effort	<i>Low/High</i>	How hard did you have to work (mentally and physically) to accomplish your level of performance?
Frustration	<i>Low/High</i>	How insecure, discouraged, irritated, stressed and annoyed versus secure, gratified, content, relaxed and complacent did you feel during the task?